

A Review on Architectures of Sense Amplifier based Flip-Flop and their Improvisations

Ram Yadav¹, Pallavee Jaiswal²

¹Department of Electronics and Communication Engineering, Dr. C. V. Raman University, India

²Department of Electronics and Communication Engineering, Dr. C. V. Raman University, India

Abstract: This paper presents a review on architecture of sense amplifier-based flip-flop (SAFF) and its improvisation. SAFF is a type of master-slave flip-flop (MSFF) and a conventional SAFF (CONV-SAFF) is composed of a Sense-Amplifier (SA) stage and a Slave R-S Latch. So, the improvisation is carried out in either SA stage or Latch stage or Both. Also, while designing a SAFF, significant factors to consider include power consumption, latency, and area. Therefore, we are reviewing the various techniques employed in SAFF architectures which improvises factors of speed of operation, delay, and area.

Keywords: Sense Amplifier based Flip-Flop (SAFF), Sense Amplifier (SA), Latch.

1. Introduction:

The most fundamental components in registers, counters, and finite state machines are flip-flops (FFs). The fundamental component of storing for single bit information is the FF. [5]. The effectiveness of the FF affects the performance of these applications, including registers, counters, and finite state machines.

If the application's area, delay, and FF's power consumption exhibit reductions, it results in decreased power usage, lower latency, and a smaller application area. The demand of the moment is to design a flipflop that excels in efficiency regarding delay, size, and power usage.

Since flipflop performance affects application performance as well, Sense Amplifier-based flipflops (SAFF) are utilized to enhance FF performance in terms of power, speed, and latency. [14].

Sense-amplifier-based flip-flop (SAFF) is one of the efficient minimal powers FFs which is widely used for low power circuits. The SAFF, first appearing in [1], is a fast flip-flop with a near-zero or negative setup time. Hence, employed SAFF is considered to improve the performance of the digital circuit in terms of high speed, reduced latency, and reduced power intake.

Basically, SAFF is a topography of Master-Slave FF (MSFF) and a conventional SAFF (CONV-SAFF) is composed of a Sense-Amplifier (SA) stage and a Slave R-S Latch [3], as shown in Fig.1. SAFF design provides nearly zero set-up time and lower clock skew. Its SA stage could record the data right after Clock's

(CK) rising edge, and its output could be maintained as the state of SN and RN, throughout CK's positive half cycle. With a near-zero or negative setup time and a reduced hold time, the SAFF can be regarded as a good candidate to substitute MSFF in the cell library for high-speed design. The schematic of a CONV-SAFF, as shown in Fig.1, composed of a SA stage and a NAND2-based set-reset (S-R) latch stage. Basically, SAFF operates as follows:

A sense amplifier speeds memory operation by sensing small initial changes in the data line and driving the stored value to the output quickly. [2]. In SAFF, the SA stage could record the data right after CK's rising edge, and its output could be maintained throughout CK's positive half cycle. [14]. The SA stage produces monotonous transitions from High to Low logic level on one of the outputs, following the rising edge of clock (CK). And the slave S-R latch captures each transition and holds the state until the next rising edge of CK arrives. In this way, the whole structure acts as a flip-flop. [18].

In detail, this SAFF works in two phases:

- 1. Pre-charge phase:** During the pre-charge phase, the internal nodes of a dynamic circuit are set to a specific voltage level, typically the complementary value of the logic level that the circuit will eventually evaluate. This is done to ensure that the circuit starts from a known state before the actual evaluation begins. Consider Fig.1; when the CK is low, the SN and RN nodes are pre-charged to the supply voltage VDD.
- 2. Evaluation phase:** The evaluation phase is where the actual logic operation takes place within a dynamic logic circuit. After the pre-charge phase, the inputs to the circuit are applied, and the circuit's response is determined based on these inputs.

Consider Fig.1 of a CONV-SAFF designed in CMOS technology; during Pre-charge phase ($CK = 0$), the internal nodes **SN** and **RN** will get charged to the supply voltage **VDD**. In the evaluation phase ($CK = 1$), actual flipflop operation occurs.

When $CK = 0$, both p-MOS transistors (MP1 & MP4) with CK as input at the Gates are ON, the charge from VDD is transferred to SN and RN nodes. Thus, the voltage of SN and RN is pre-charged to VDD while the CK is low; and the output data are maintained by the latch.

At the rising edge of CK (when $CK = 1$), the pre-charge transistors MP1 and MP4 are turned OFF and MN6 is turned ON. One of the pre-charge nodes (SN and RN) is discharged to zero while the other node remains VDD, depending on the input data applied at node D. The transition from output Q and QN to the supply voltage's high (VDD) or low (VSS), depends on the state of the nodes RN and SN, which drive the slave S-R latch. The always-ON transistor MN3, maintain the output of the SA through SN and RN state, when CK is high.

For example, SN is discharged to 0 in response to $D = 1$ at the rising edge of CK, and SN needs to be maintained at 0 during the positive half cycle of CK. D may change to 0 during the positive half cycle, thus an alternate path to 0 should be provided to SN, and MN3 works at this time. MN3 provides alternate path to ground (GND) to complete this circuit.

This is the working of a CONV-SAFF.

Fig.1. Schematic of a CONV-SAFF

The main trouble associated with the CONV-SAFF is the

unbalanced delay of the S-R latch as well as the large power of the pre-charge operation. Moreover, the always-ON transistor decreases the robustness of the SAFF at low supply voltages.

To improve the factor of power consumption, latency, and speed of SAFF circuit, improvisation is carried out in either or both of its SA stage and Latch stage. So, in this paper we have discussed in details the various techniques employed in SAFF design so far, to improve the above factors.

In the remainder of this paper, we will be covering Literature Survey and Comparison with CONV-SAFF; and in the latter part of this paper the Conclusion & Future Scope and the References.

2. Literature Survey of SAFF:

To improvise SAFF working, many better designs proposed mending the architecture of CONV-SAFF; some of which are discussed in the paper till present.

In [3], Nikolic et al. proposed a SAFF with improved latch while retaining the SA stage as that of CONV-SAFF. The latch is composed of two inverters and several complex logics which eliminates the delay dependence between Q and QN as in the CONV-SAFF, and also decrease the delay of the overall SAFF design. The schematic of Nikolic's latch is shown in Figure 2.

Fig. 2. Nikolic's Latch

Review: In [3], the inversion of SN and RN are carried out to make four signals as SN, RN, S and R. These signals are used to generate the outputs Q and QN directly. Thus, the interdependence between Q and QN is eliminated and the CK-to-Q delay is decreased. But the delay of the inverters and complex logic of the design cannot be ignored, the optimization of the delay in this way may not meet the expectations.

In [4], Kim et al. proposed a SAFF with SA of CONV-SAFF and a latch of two N-C2MOS circuits with two pairs of cross-coupled inverters to achieve the fast transition as shown in Fig. 3.

Fig.3. Kim's Latch

Review: [4] has two drawbacks: (1) When the previous state of output Q and input D are both high, the output Q must remain high at the next rising edge of CK, but because of the discharge of the node SN has not been completed, the pull-down path of Q is ON, through which a glitch occurs; (2) The cross-coupled inverter at the output Q generate contention current, which raise the power consumption and the delay.

In [5], Strollo et al. proposed a SAFF which combined the CONV-SAFF and Kim's SAFF to attain both fast and glitch-free operation. The schematic of Strollo's SAFF is shown in Fig. 4.

Fig.4. Strollo's SAFF: (a) SA stage (b) Latch stage

In [5], to reduce the power consumption and D-to-Q latency, they drive the symmetric latch directly with only SN and RN, removing their inversion signals (S & N).

Review: Despite the power reduction by this modification, a signal conflict in the latching stage may result in increased latency. For example, if a high input arrives when Q is low, during the period in which QN is being pulled down through M19-M21 after the rising clock edge, M16 stays ON and fights

against the pull-down of QN until SN is discharged to raise Q, which may result in a longer falling latency of the outputs. Moreover, the problem related to the shorting device (M4) like Nikolic's SAFF [3] still causes overheads in terms of power, latency, and area.

In [6], Ahmadi et al. instead of modifying latch in CONV-SAFF, they improved the SA stage by adding the delay transistor in it, equating the rise and fall delays of the node SN and RN.

In [9], Lin et al. improved the latch of [4] to a single-ended structure while retaining SA as of CONV-SAFF. Lin's Latch is shown in Fig.5.

Fig.5. Lin's Latch

Review: In [9], since there are few logics between SN and the output Q, hence the delay and power consumption of this kind of SAFF is greatly reduced compared with that of the CONV-SAFF. In spite of this, there is a big glitch occurs when the output Q and the next data input are both high, and this glitch will increase the power consumption of the SAFF. Moreover, the current contention of the back-to-back inverters in the latch will raise the power consumption too.

All these SAFFs [3]-[6], [9], employed SA stage of CONV-SAFF, suffers from the low voltage operation problem due to the always-ON transistor MN3 of the SA stage of CONV-SAFF shown in Fig.1.

To address this problem, Jeong et al. in [11] proposed a SAFF with transition completion detection (SAFF-TCD) i.e., TC signal applied to always-ON transistor (MN6, here) shown in Fig. 6.

Fig.6. Jeong's SAFF (a) SA (b) Latch

SAFF-TCD [11] overcomes the problem related to the shorting device, by detecting the transitions of SN and RN. When CK=0, both SN and RN are pre-charged to high, letting transition completion signal TC be low and transistor MN6 be OFF. So, the pull-down evaluation of SN or RN is separately performed from each other, necessitating no sizing issue of MN6. After the pull-down of SN or RN, TC goes high to turn MN6 ON for static operation.

Review: Although SAFF-TCD can avoid the sizing issue of MN6, the power consumption and latency show limited improvements compared to Strollo's SAFF, as mentioned in [11].

In [12], Pandey K. et al. proposes a SAFF with symmetric latch design, as shown in Fig.7.

Fig.7. Pandey's SAFF: (a) SA (b) Latch

Here when input data $D = 0$ (low), SB sets to high, and if $D = 1$ (high), RB will be set to high. Therefore, this technique is also known as conditional pre-charging, applied to the master sensing stage of the designed SAFF to control the redundant transition of the data in the internal nodes. P1 and P2 are input controlled transistors, embedded at the pre-charging path of internal nodes SB, RB respectively. If D is high for N cycles, node SB is discharged only at the initial stage of (N-1) cycles which means that SB floats for low state of CLOCK or when DB is fed with low state at high state of CLOCK meanwhile RB needed to be pre-charged only at the initial phase of the simulation and remains high for rest of the cycles.

Review: Since the pre-charging is controlled conditionally during this entire process, the pull-down of the critical path of internal nodes SB, RB is reduced, as it now only consists of a single transistor. Due to this fact, circuits discharging time reduces which results in high performance in the sensing stage.

In [14], Heng et al. observed that the SA stage in the CONV-SAFF required to charge all the internal nodes during pre-charge operation, and the nodes such as N1, N2, and N3 in Fig.1 are discharged to VSS (i.e., low) during the data-capturing operation, irrespective of what the input data are. Also, the pre-charge operation of nodes N1, N2 and N3 has no practical effect on the function of the SA and is a waste of power. So, [14] applied a conditional cut-off strategy to the latch to cut-off power supply at these nodes during pre-charge phase to achieve glitch-free and contention-free operation.

Fig.8. Heng's SAFF: (a) SA (b) Latch

[14] improvised the structure of the SA; the NMOS controlled by CK (MN5 in Fig.1) is split into two (MN5 and MN6 in Fig. 8) and moved to connect directly to the back-to-back inverter, as shown in Fig.8. Due to this improvisation, the transistors MN5 and MN6 are OFF when CK is low and thus the nodes (N1 and N2) related to transistors MN3 and MN4 no longer needed to be charged during the pre-charge operation. Thus, the power of the pre-charge operation is greatly reduced and of the proposed SAFF.

[14] also applied a new single-ended latch to the proposed SAFF with the advantages of Strollo's latch [5] and Lin's latch [9] to reach fast and energy efficient operation. Furthermore, the proposed SAFF in [14] can provide low voltage operation by adopting MTCMOS optimization.

Review: But, in [14], further reduction in power consumption can be achieved by preventing transition leakage.

In [18], Yuan et al. proposed a SAFF in 55nm CMOS technology by modifying both the SA stage and the latch, as shown in Fig.9.

Fig.9. Yuan's SAFF

As per [18], the cause of continuous power consumption in the SA stage is the pre-charge of SN and RN to VDD every time

when CK is low until the input D switches. To avoid it, [18] introduced two transistors, MP5 and MP6 in the proposed design to cooperate with MN4 and MN5, which results in the controlled pre-charge of the SN and RN as determined by the switching operation of the input D and not by CK. Thus, avoiding the continuous charge and discharge of SN and RN with the CK transition while the input remains unchanged for a long time, avoiding additional power consumption overhead.

In [18], the proposed latch structure, the leakage current is reduced with the insertion of the MP7, MN7, and MN10 as shown in Fig.9. The inverter-like structure design ensures the node's fast charge, and the pull-down path design with shut-off transistor MN10, reduces the leakage current and ensures the correct function of the latch structure.

Review: Although, Yuan's SAFF [18] provided a solution to continuous pre-charge power consumption but, it is observed that the switching and short-circuit leakage power plays a significant role in the high-frequency dynamic transition of inputs. So, to effectively control the leakage power due to transition, the arrangement should be provided within the SA stage also rather than only in the slave latch of a SAFF. Also, [18] proposed the design in CMOS, which may suffer from the low voltage operation problem.

Thus, we have discussed the improvisations carried out in SAFF design till now.

3. Conclusion & Future Scope:

Thus, it can be concluded as, most of the SAFF design suffers either of the (a) low voltage operation problem, (b) continuous pre-charge power consumption, (c) leakage current arising out of switching, short-circuit and data transition, (d) increased delay. Therefore, improvisation in SAFF should be carried out in its architecture and in the technology used, to cover all these problems.

The demand for high-speed operation of electronic systems requires faster data storing element; and flip-flops (FFs) are considered to be the basic memory element of a digital system. Along with speed, other requirements are its low latency, low power consumption, and lesser area.

SAFF is one of the efficient minimal powers FFs, which is widely used for low power circuits. The SAFF is a fast flip-flop with a near-zero or negative setup time. Hence, employing the SAFF improves the performance of the digital circuit in terms of high speed, reduced latency, and reduced power intake.

Therefore, employing SAFF with improved design in digital circuitry may become a revolutionary change in the electronic industry to achieve the present need.

4. References

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AUTHORS

Ram Yadav is currently a Student of Master of Technology in VLSI Branch of Electronics and Communication Engineering Department at Dr. C. V. Raman University (CVRU), Bilaspur, Chhattisgarh State, India. Prior to this, he completed his Bachelor of Engineering in Electronics & Telecommunication Engineering from Chhattisgarh Swami Vivekananda Technical University (CSVTU), Bhilai, Durg District, Chhattisgarh State, India.

Corresponding Author.

Pallavee Jaiswal is Assistant Professor in the Department of Electronics and Communication Engineering, Dr. C. V. Raman University (CVRU), Bilaspur, Chhattisgarh State, India. She received her B.E. Degree in Electronics and Telecommunication Engineering From GEC, Raipur (C.G.), India & MTech Degree in Digital Communication from Dr. C. V. Raman University, Bilaspur (C.G.), India. She is pursuing her PhD in Electronics and Communication Engineering from Dr. C. V. Raman University, Bilaspur. She is UGC -NET qualified. She has more 10 Years of teaching experience. She has published more than 15 paper in the reputed journals. Her research interests cover Signal Processing, Image Processing, Speech Processing.

